

Trade Union Contribution in Overcoming Industrial Relations Problems

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Abstract

One important factor in achieving company goals is fostering healthy industrial relations between employees and companies. Considering that employees play an important role in achieving company goals, it is appropriate for employees to receive commensurate compensation from the company. However, in reality employees often protest because they feel their welfare is not appropriate, on the other hand the company also has difficulty realizing employee desires. To overcome these problems, a mediator is needed to bridge the problems faced by both parties. Such mediators are for example the department of labor and trade unions.

This research was conducted with the aim to find out how much the contribution made by trade unions in overcoming problems related to industrial relations. The object of this study is employees at PT. KahatexRancaekek, Bandung Regency taken randomly as many as 80 people. The instruments of the research are in the form of questionnaires that have been tested for validity and reliability, while for large contributions used regression analysis.

Keywords: Trade Unions, Industrial Relations

I. INTRODUCTION

Industrial relations is an important factor in efforts to achieve company goals. Industrial relations itself involves several parties within the scope of the company's work, where labor is one of the parties involved. Manpower plays an important role in achieving company goals, therefore workers have the right to receive compensation for the performance given. But over time did not escape from labor problems, where workers often protest against the employer's place in providing unfair welfare and deviations committed by employers against workers who are not in accordance with the provisions of the applicable law in this country . In terms of welfare, certainly not escape the problems faced by companies, one of which is PT. Kahatex, located in Rancaekek, Bandung Regency.

Employees at the company still do not feel well-being, other than that some policies from management sometimes harm other parties such as termination of employment done because of disharmony between employees and managers so that the decision taken is a layoff unilaterally, from several problems that occur also all are violations of collective labor agreements carried out both by employees and from the manager himself, not only that in an agreed work agreement some problems may occur that deviate from the agreed terms. Therefore, the employees of PT. Kahatex form an organization that is a trade union as a form of protection of the rights and obligations of its employees where if its members have not felt welfare then the union is obliged to call for injustice and help find a solution.

The role of trade unions themselves is very important for employees and managers in protecting their rights and obligations, besides that trade unions are the right place for managers to make decisions in the interests of employers and workers where those decisions concern the decent life of their employees. These trade unions were also formed on the basis of realizing the welfare of workers and their families, to achieve this they were treated with a vehicle for a strong struggle, able to channel aspirations and unite all the potential of diverse workers, and be actively involved in the organization of the company.

II. LITERATURE

2.1. Understanding Trade Unions

Trade unions are open social systems that pursue goals and are often influenced by the external environment. Trade unions are a vehicle for employees as a vehicle to participate in the company. Employee participation in relation to work relations can be done directly or through a representative system in the form of trade unions. Therefore, employee participation in work relationships is also a manifestation of the rights and impressions of employees in organizing and issuing opinions guaranteed by the constitution and laws. Therefore, in legal issues unions have a broad goal, firstly, to make employees as trade unions accountable for the use of detailed requirements, secondly, the law tries to make trade unions more democratic by giving rights certain members.

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2.1.1. The Essence of Trade Unions

A union is an organization formed from, by and for workers both in companies and outside the company, which is free, independent, democratic, and responsible for fighting for, defending and protecting the rights and interests of workers and their families. In the business world, negotiations that occur between management and workers must be based on the same perception and both parties must be determined and have good faith to foster and maintain harmonious relations. In an organization, there are 2 types of decisions that are treated as similar perceptions from all parties involved:

1. A series of decisions which are the prerogative of one of the parties who took them, in this case management or workers, without the interference of other parties.
2. The forms and types of various institutions that are made together.

2.1.2. The purpose of the union

Some general objectives characterize workers' movements as a whole:

1. Guarantee and if possible improve the standard of living and economic status of its members
2. Ensuring individual security from threats and situations that can arise due to market fluctuations, technological changes, or management decisions
3. Influencing power relations in the social system in ways that support that do not harm the development and objectives of the union
4. Promote the welfare of all those who work for a living, whether they are for union members or not
5. Create mechanisms to counteract the use of subjective or arbitrary policies or practices in the workplace.

2.2 Definition of Industrial Relations

Industrial relations is a relationship between all parties or stakeholders who are related and have an interest in the production process or company services. In Indonesia industrial relations is regulated by labor law number 13 of 2003 concerning manpower. Article 1 of the UUK states that what is meant by industrial relations is a system of relationships formed between actors in the process of producing goods / services consisting of elements of the constitution of the Republic of Indonesia 1945.

2.2.1. Types of industrial relations disputes

Under Article 2 of the PHI Law, the types of industrial relations include (1) disputes over rights, (2) disputes of interest, (3) disputes over termination of employment, and (4) disputes between trade unions in only one company.

2.2.2. Industrial Relations Facilities

Some of the facilities and institutions are (1) company regulations, (2) bipartite institutions, (3) Trade Unions, (4) collective labor agreements, (5) employers' associations, (6) tripartite institutions, (7) relationship dispute settlement institutions industrial, 8. Labor Regulations, (9) industrial relations education.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

In collecting data taken as discussion material, the author uses qualitative research methods. This study uses a qualitative form with a descriptive approach to a single embedded case, where researchers only examine one problem, namely the role of trade unions in solving industrial relations problems in PT. Kahatex. The reasons for choosing this strategy are based on the following matters:

- a. This study is called singular meaning in this study only examines one problem, namely the extent to which the role of trade unions in solving industrial relations problems at PT. Kahatex
- b. This research is called fixed because the goals and objectives and problems have been determined before the researcher went into the field or place of research so that the data collection activities are more directed based on the research objectives.

3.1. Research design

This type of research conducted at the writing of this study is descriptive and verification research, where descriptive research according to Kuncoro (2013: 12) is research that includes collecting data to test hypotheses or answer questions about the final status of the research subject. The most common type of descriptive research involves evaluating the attitudes or opinions of individuals, organizations, circumstances or procedures.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The data collection process was designed through questionnaires consisting of 8 statements for the union variable (X), and 10 statements for the industrial relations variable (Y). Validity testing is carried out on the statements in the questionnaire by using the correlation method between the statement score with the total score construct or variable (Product Pearson Moment), based on the results of the validity test all the values of the questionnaire validity coefficient (r) exceeds 0.2199 so that it is declared valid or feasible to use, so also with the validity test for industrial relations

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variables obtained all the values of the questionnaire validity coefficient (r) exceeds 0.2199 so that it is declared valid or feasible to use.

4.1. Recapitulation of Respondents' Answers

The following is a general description of respondents' responses regarding trade unions in the table:

Table 1. Recapitulation of Respondents' Responses Regarding Trade Unions (X)

No.	Statement	Score
1.	Unions distinguish between the treatment of members and ordinary employees	206
2.	Your rights as an employee are protected by the union	280
3.	Bosses have the right to impose sanctions or dismissals on employees or union members who violate the rules	259
4.	Some management policies harm employees	280
5.	Trade unions as representatives in the procedure for raising problems or complaints	259
6.	The trade union settlement of the problem reached a fair agreement	276
7.	You feel safe in your organization	237
8.	Wages, hours of work and benefits are in accordance with agreements agreed with the company	289
Total Score		2086
Ideal Value		3200

Table 1 above shows the total promotion value of 2086, while the ideal value is 3200; or in other words the total promotion value is 0.65 (65%) of the ideal value. This value is included in the category of sufficient.

4.2. Industrial Relations at PT. Kahatex

The following is a general description of respondents' responses regarding industrial relations in the table:

Table 2. Recapitulation of Respondents' Responses Regarding Industrial Relations (Y)

No.	Statement	Score
1.	Company gives contribution to achieving the welfare of workers' lives	280
2.	Workers provide an important role for the company in carrying out operational activities	297
3.	Trade unions maintain a relationship between companies and workers	206
4.	The government helps workers in achieving the welfare of labor	241
5.	Trade unions provide protection, defense of the rights and interests of workers	301
6.	Employers' organizations need to be formed to create and maintain industrial relations	265
7.	Effective cooperation institutions as a forum for communication and deliberation between union representatives and companies	264
8.	The rights and obligations of both parties are clearly detailed in the PKB	268
9.	The terms of employment, rights and obligations of both parties are mutually binding and beneficial	264
10.	The provisions in the Collective Labor Agreement are not contrary to the law	278
Total Score		2664
Ideal Value		4000

Table 2. above shows the total industrial relations value of 2664, while the ideal value of 4000; or in other words the total performance value is 0.66 (66%) of the ideal value. This value is included in the category of sufficient.

4.3. Simple Regression Analysis

By using the help of a statistical software program application on a computer, the output of simple linear regression calculation results is obtained as follows:

Table 3. Results of Calculation of Regression Equation Coefficient Values

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	9,211	2,365		3,895	,000
SP	,959	,089	,773	10,765	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Hubungan Industrial

Based on the above output we get constant values and regression coefficients so that a simple linear regression equation can be formed as follows $Y = 9,211 + 0,959X$

4.4. Correlation Coefficient Analysis

Based on data processing using statistical software, the correlation coefficient results are obtained as follows:

Table 4. Results of Correlation Coefficient Calculation Results
Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,773 ^a	,598	,593	4,080

a. Predictors: (Constant), SerikatPekerja

From the above analysis it can be seen that the value of the correlation coefficient (R) is 0.773 which indicates a strong relationship between the independent variables simultaneously with the dependent variable.

4.5. Analysis of the Coefficient of Determination

After knowing the R value, the coefficient of determination can be calculated using the following formula:

Table 5. Determination Coefficient Results

Model Summary				
R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	
,773 ^a	,598	,593	4,080	

The coefficient of determination of 59.8% means that trade unions influence 59.8% of industrial relations, and the remaining 40.2% is influenced by other variables not examined in this study.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on observations obtained 3 conclusions, namely,

1. The role of trade unions in PT. Kahatex is already maximal enough to fight for the wages, salaries and benefits of its members that are relatively low.
2. Industrial relations that occur at PT. Kahatex has several problems, including wages and salaries that are still relatively low and termination of employment unilaterally.
3. The resolution of industrial relations problems carried out by trade unions is as follows (a) bipartite negotiations, (b) resolution through mediation, (c) resolution through conciliation, and (d) resolution by judges.

REFERENCES

- [1] Aninditiya, RahadianDimas, et al. (2015), Pengaruh Perjanjian Kerjasama Terhadap Hak-hak Karyawan dan Kepuasan Kerja, *Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis (JAB)*. Vol. 28 No. 1.
- [2] Dessler, G. (2015), *Human Resource Management*, edisi 14
- [3] Gupta, Abhishek dan Neetu Gupta. (2013), *Journal Account Mark-The 21st Century Trade Union Challenges in India*, page 2:1
- [4] Gupta, Abishek. (2013), *Journal Bussines Finance-Impact of Trade Unionism on Indian Society*. No 01 page 38-41
- [5] Kuncoro, M. (2013), *Metode Riset untuk Bisnis & Ekonomi*, ed.4, Jakarta: Erlangga.

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- [6] Kasmir.(2016), *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia (Teori dan Praktik)*, Jakarta: Rajawali Pers.
- [7] Ndraha, Taliziduhu. (2012), *Pengantar Teori Pengembangan Sumber Daya Manusia*, cetakan ke-2, Jakarta : Rineka Cipta.
- [8] Ningsih, Nia Oktavia dkk. (2015) Peran Serikat Pekerja dan Manajemen Dalam Membina Hubungan Industrial (Studi pada PG. Kebon Agung Malang), *Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis*. Vol. 24 No. 1.
- [9] Rivai, Veithzal. (2014), *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Untuk Perusahaan: Dari Teori Ke Praktik*, Jakarta: Rajawali pers.
- [10] Utami, Tanti Kiranaet all. (2013), Peran Serikat Pekerja dalam Penyelesaian Perselisihan Pemutusan Hubungan Kerja, *Jurnal Wawasan Hukum*. Vol. 28 No. 01.
- [11] Yuniarsih, Tjutju. (2016), *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia (Teori, Aplikasi, Isu Penelitian)*, Bandung: Alfabeta.